

Role of Job Crafting & Work Engagement: Application of Person Job (P-J) Fit

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Abstract

Work is a substantial trait that plays an important preponderance people's lives as it significantly contributes to the maintenance of a quality life. Employees who feel motivated at work after finding it meaningful they also contribute to the organizations. At national level, in countries like Pakistan there is dire need of engagement at work place. This study is conducted on the employees who are rendering services in public sector universities in Pakistan, through Person Job fit to provide recommendations and suggestions for the governing bodies like HEC and policy makers at national level to make changes in the legislation. The results of correlation between mediator and independent variable ($r = .605$, $p = 0.000$), mediator and dependent variable ($r = .470$, $p = 0.00$) and dependent and independent variable ($r = .530$, $p = 0.00$) implies that the faculty members of the public sector universities who craft their jobs are more engaged at work when they find they find themselves fit on the job. Regression analysis results have revealed that person job fit mediated the relation between job crafting & work engagement.

Keywords: job crafting, work engagement, work place

1. Introduction

Today in this fast-moving working environment a person who is working, spends one-third of this day at work, i.e. eight hours. Earlier jobs were considered as the combination of different tasks when given to the workers, they were supposed to trace the job description as framed by the managers.

Strauss & Parker (2014) elaborates that today the changes in work are made by bringing change in its structure and performance. The arrangement of work has an important effect on the mental health of the workers as the work has important link with the resources of survival, access to relational connections. Moreover, according to the research done by Taylor, task simplification and standardization mainly focused on Job design researches but this was criticized later on (Parker et al. 2018). Employees who feel motivated at work after finding it meaningful (Steger et al., 2012). Moreover, earlier researches has explained importance of task simplification & regularization that focused on Job design theories but this was criticized later on (Parker et al. 2018).

Then, there came an idea of job redesign that was based on the employee's motivations (Lee and Lee, 2018) and it was further altered by including the proactive behavior of the employees. (Hornung et al., 2010). Currently, the researchers are focusing in the fact that how much proactive employees are to bring changes in the features of their job and their environment Frese et al. (2007).

Emerging nations like Pakistan require more engagement at job precisely in the education sector which is considered as the main pillar behind all kinds of advancements. Hence, this research has explored the association among job crafting & work engagement of employees/workers rendering services in public sector HEIs / universities in Pakistan, with a mediation of P-J fit to provide recommendations and suggestions for the governing bodies like HEC and policy makers at national level to make changes in the legislation.

2. Literature Review

Researchers have given importance to job design and mentioned that Job design will effect managers as well as the employees of the organizations (Fuller et al. 2006). In general, person-environment fit behavior may be considered as a key for employees to contrast their abilities and needs with demands & opportunities provided at work place surroundings (Parker & Collins, 2010).

Job related satisfaction that is gained through positive mental condition known as engagement at work which is defined as vigor, dedication & absorption. Without any fear of coercion employees immerse in their job roles Schaufeli et al. (2002).

According to job crafting positively influences work engagement (Tims et al. 2014). Job crafting is actually a modification of tasks or job characteristics as per Roczniowski and Bakker (2016). Employees will work best as per their availability, when both the employees and job have mutual suitability with their job. Therefore, the Cable and DeRue (2002) have explained that the Person-job fit is a state defined as an employee's ability or suitability with job demands, individual needs, and what the job can provide to employees. According to Scroggins (2008) and Hamid & Yahya (2011), there is no prior work which analyzes the effects P-J fit on employee engagement.

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3. Conceptual Framework & Hypothesis

3.1. Concept of Job crafting

In job crafting employees better contest their needs, goals & surroundings according to their job as explained by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001).

It is also defined as a change made by the employees' by bringing physical, cognitive and relational changes and along with that the employee made his work compatible with the features of his personality Ingusci, Callea, Chirumbolo & Urbini (2016). Thus, employees become more proactive in order to bring the change in their real work life as explained by Tims & Bakker (2016). Thus this customization is known as job crafting. The employees can bring relational, cognitive and physical on their jobs as explained by Bakker et al. (2012a).

- Physical variation is defined as bringing change in the scope, arrangement or the numbers of jobs.
- Cognitive change is defined as how people view their jobs.
- Relational change is defined as that how people meet at their work place.

3.2. Job crafting & Work Engagement

Crafting of job is carried out by the workers when he fully understands the realization of autonomous and proactive change.

The previous researches considered the idea of Job crafting as an individual concept but later on the research work of Leana (2009) considered impact of collaborative job crafting is much more powerful and effective in relation to the individual activity. Then Leana (2009) further explained the concept that due to shared working processes and experiences of common events the employees can "jointly determine how they can alter their work to meet the shared goal or objective". Thus it revealed that there are two constructs one is individual and the other is collaborative.

In **individual crafting** the employees efficiently bring change in their jobs. According to McClelland et al. (2014) there is scarcity of research studies on the collaborative crafting. Whereas in **collaborative job crafting** group members with the mutual efforts will increase social & structural job assets inclusive of difficult job needs & decreases the job needs which hinders work processes. It has also paved way for the individual job crafting:

In literature, engagement at work is defined as a positive work related psychological state categorized by the dedication, absorption and vigor (Schaufeli et. al., 2002).

- Schaufeli & Bakker (2004) defined Vigor as high level of energy depicted by the employee at work.
- Dedication refers to the involvement of employee at work where he feels the importance and pride in his work.
- Absorption is characterized by means of full focus, attention and properly captivated in one's work.

Those who are engaged, they outperform. Moreover, the employees who are intrinsically motivated bring innovation at their workplace (Chang et al. 2013). This will not only increase the individual or team level performance but also increases the organizational level performance because they will provide competitive advantage to the organizations in relation to job satisfaction, low turnover intentions, customer satisfaction and above all profitability.

Researchers including Schaufeli et. al. (2004) emphasized more on conceptualizing the positive valence of engagement. Bakker (2008) suggested that the employees having high work engagement experience positive impacts including joy, happiness and zeal as they find their work more interesting and meaningful. Macey & Schneider (2008) elucidated that "the construct of engagement becomes due to the sense of energy and enthusiasm".

According to Perrin (2003), Kular et. al. (2008) and Blessing White (2011) an empirical study depicted that there are only 17% of employees are engaged at their work place in US. Globally 31% are engaged and in Asia only 26% of employees are engaged. Thus based on above description, the following hypotheses is proposed:

H1: Job crafting is significantly positively related to work engagement.

3.3. Concept of Person Job (P-J) Fit

Person Job (P-J) fit is described as suitability of features of a worker with the work environment. Edwards (1991) explained that P-J fit is based on two constructs of conceptualizations which are further explained by Cable and DeRue (2002), **Needs-supplies fit** refers to the congruence between the preferences, rewards, desires and needs received at the work place whereas the **Demands-Abilities fit** referred it to the similarity that exists among demands of job and KSAs (knowledge, skills & abilities) of employees. Cable & DeRue (2002).

3.4. Relationship between Person Job (P-J) Fit & Job Crafting

Researchers have mentioned that crafting of job permits the employees to apt their KSAs (knowledge, skills & abilities) according to their jobs Leana (2009). Job Crafting depicts a positive impact on employees admissible work abilities Kira et al., (2010). Employees are actively adjusting their own work environment as well as employees connect with other employees to achieve the shared goals. Therefore, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2: Job crafting is positively related to Person job (P-J) fit

3.5. Mediating role of Person Job fit (P-J)

The person environment (P-E) fit theory & person job fit highlights the suitability between job traits and person capability to function the undertaking will reinforce employees’ engagement to their work, particularly the worker will be extra dedicated to the job (Allen and Meyer, 1997. Moreover, it is also described as suitability of employee required to do the job and employees in order to fit them as per the job requirement.

Thus, following hypotheses are proposed:

H3: Person job (P-J) fit and work engagement are positively correlated

H4: Person job (P-J) fit mediates the relationship among job crafting & work engagement

4. Methodology

Cross-sectional survey design has been used in this study as the data is collected at one point of time. The population included male and female teachers of public sector universities located in Lahore. Data was collected from the Three Public University teachers of Lahore, Pakistan. Three hundred & seventy (370) questionnaires were administered physically. Total 332 university teachers returned the filled questionnaires showing a response rate of 89.72%. 76 teachers from University of Education, Lahore gave their response, 155 faculty members responded from the University of the Punjab Lahore, and 101 Teachers from the University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences. Eight (8) questionnaires having incomplete information were not considered. Remaining Three hundred & twenty four (324) survey questionnaires were used for research purpose. Universities were selected randomly however; teachers’ sample was drawn through purposive sampling and then random sampling.

The data has been gathered from the respondents and afterwards coded and entered into SPSS for correlation and regression analysis using “Process” macro.

After gathering the data from respondents, it was coded and entered into SPSS for further regression, correlation and mediation analysis.

4.1. Measures

In order to conduct this study, before the data collection a pilot study was done. Using 12 items scale as given by Leana (2009) and the scores of reliability measures are mentioned in table. Example of Individual job crafting is ‘Introduce new approaches on your own to improve your work’; collaborative job crafting is ‘Decide together with your coworkers to organize special events on your own’. Five point (5) Likert scale has been used that ranges between “Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree” to record responses from the participants.

Table 1 depicts that all the dimensions of the Independent variable has shown a good reliability value:

Table 1: Reliability of Job Crafting Scale

	No of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha’s Value
Individual Job Crafting	6	.757
Collaborative Job Crafting	6	.923

4.2. Work Engagement

The Work engagement scale of Utrecht Work Engagement Scale Schaufeli et al. (2002), was used to measure work engagement, which has three subscales: Vigor measured through six items, Dedication & absorption through five & six items respectively. The example of items are “At my work, I feel bursting with energy, to me, my job is challenging and When I am working, I forget everything else around me” respectively. In this study, five point (5) Likert scale has been used that range between “Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree” for the recoding of the participant’s responses. **Table 2** depicts that all the dimensions of the Independent variable has shown a good reliability value:

Table Number 2: Reliability of Work Engagement Scale

	Number of items	Cronbach’s Alpha’s Value
Work Engagement	17	0.925

4.3. Person Job (P-J) fit

Though, to measure the person job fit a 9-item scale was developed by Brkich et al. (2002) Example of person job fit is “My current job is not really me and “This job is not really what I would like to be doing”. Five point Likert scale ranging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree” was used to record the participant’s responses. Table 3 depicts that it has shown a good reliability value:

Table 3: Person Job fit Reliability Score

	Number of items	Cronbach’s Alpha’s Value
Person Job (P-J) fit	9	.778

5. Final Results for analysis of study

Table 4 Pearson Correlation (Sample N=324)

Final Results for analysis of study

Table 4 Pearson Correlation

(Sample N=324)

		Correlations		
		Person Job Fit	Work Engagement	Job Crafting
Person Job Fit	Pearson Correlation	1	.470**	.605**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
Work Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.470**	1	.530**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
Job Crafting	Pearson Correlation	.605**	.530**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results as depicted in Table 4, showed Pearson correlation among P-J fit & job crafting (r= .605, p=0.00) which explains a positive significant relationship between two variables. The correlation value between P-J fit & work engagement explains a positive significant relationship (r=.470, p=0.00). Likewise, the value of correlation among between Work engagement & Job crafting (r=.530 p=0.00) explains a positive significant relationship.

Hence, in light of above mentioned results the following hypotheses are accepted:

- H1: Job crafting is significantly positively related to work engagement.
- H2: Job crafting is positively related to P-J fit.
- H3: Person job (P-J) fit and work engagement is positively correlated.
- H4: Person job (P-J) fit mediates the relationship among job crafting & work engagement.

5.1. Testing Mediation with Regression Analysis using Process in SPSS

To test the hypothesis SPSS macro has been used as developed Andrew Hayes (Hayes & Rockwood, 2017) in order to test an indirect effect. In this study, predictor is job crafting, person job fit is mediator & work engagement is the final outcome. Here is a picture of the model along with the results:

The hypotheses were investigated through analysis where Person job fit mediates the effect of job crafting on work engagement. Results indicated that job crafting is a significant predictor of person job fit, B = .62, SE = .39, 95%CI [.51, .72], β = .53, p = .00, and that person job fit is a significant predictor of work engagement, B = .43, SE = .04, 95% CI[.034,..52], β = .46, p = .00. Mediation hypothesis has been supported by these results. Moreover, Job crafting is a significant predictor of satisfaction after controlling for the mediator, person job fit, B = .21, SE = .05, 95%CI[.10,.31], β = .20, p = .00, consistent with full mediation. Approximately 39% of variance in work engagement has been accounted for by the predictors (R2 = .39). The indirect effect was tested using a percentile bootstrap estimation approach with 5000 samples Shrout & Bolger (2002), implemented with PROCESS macro Version 4

given by Hayes (2022). These results indicated the indirect coefficient is significant, $B = .26$, $SE = .03$, $95\% CI [.19,.34]$, completely standardized $\beta = .26$. Job crafting was associated with work engagement scores that were approximately .26 points higher as mediated by person job fit.

Table 5: Results

OUTCOME VARIABLE:									
PJ									
Model Summary									
R	R-	MSE	F	df1	df2	p			
5300	.2809	.0891	125.7731	1.000	322.0000	.0000			
Model									
		Coeff	s.e	t	P	LLCI	ULCI		
Outcome		1.6579	.2567	6.4585	.0000	1.1529	2.1630		
JC		.6504	.2567	11.2149	.0000	.5116	.7892		
Standardized coefficients									
		Coeff							
JC		.5300							
OUTCOME VARIABLE:									
WE									
Model Summary									
R	R-	MSE	F	df1	df2	p			
.6297	.3966	.0577	105.4776	2.0000	321.0000	.0000			
Model									
		Coeff	se	t	p	LCCI	ULCI		
Out,Estd	1.7646	.2195	8.0408	.0000	1.3329	2.19664			
JC		.2130	.0525	4.0994	.0001	.1098	.3162		
PJ		.4337	.0448	9.6744	.0000	.3455	.5219		
Standardized coefficients									
		Coeff							
JC		.2076							
PJ		.4946							
TOTAL EFFECT MODEL:									
OUTCOME VARIABLE:									
WE									
Model Summary									
R	R-	MSE	F	df1	df2	p			
.4697	.2206	.0742	91.1495	1.0000	322.0000	.0000			
Model									
		Coeff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI		
Out,Estd	2.4836	.2343	10.5999	.0000	2.0226	2.9446			
JC		.4820	.0505	9.5472	.0000	.3827	.5814		
Standardized coefficients									
		Coeff							
JC		.4697							

Compete effect including Direct and indirect effects of X on Y

Total Effect							
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	e.es	
.4820	.0505	9.5472	.0000	.3827	.5814	.4697	
Direct Effect							
Effect	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	e_es	
21.30	.0525	4.0594	.0001	.1098	.3162	.2076	
Indirect Effect							
Effect	BeetSE	BeetLLCI		BeetULCI			
PJ	.2690	.0392	.1934		.3503		
Completely standardized indirect effect(s) of X on Y:							
Effect	BeetSE	BeetLLCI		BeetULCI			
PJ	.2622	.0370	.1923		.3378		
*Level of confidence for all confidence intervals in output: 95.0000							

*Number of heoes 1ran samples fue percentile bus of Strap confidence interval 5000

5.2. Relationship between Job crafting & work engagement through Person Job fit

Thus, overall model comprising of three factors (i.e. Job crafting, Person Job fit & Work Engagement) is accepted, as given in the table 5. In short, the Person job fit fully mediated the relationship between Job crafting and work engagement.

6. Conclusion

The prime objective of this research was to explore the relationship between job crafting, work engagement & person job fit. The study was performed to find out the role of person job fit as a mediator among job crafting & engagement of employees at who are rendering services in public sector universities in Pakistan. Results of the Pearson correlation between Person Job fit and Job crafting ($r=.605$, $p=0.00$) explains a significant positive relationship. The correlation value between Person Job fit and Work engagement also showed a positive significant positive relationship ($r=.470$, $p=0.00$). Similarly the correlation value between Work engagement and Job crafting ($r=.530$ $p=0.00$) explains the significant positive relationship. The analysis results have revealed that person job fit has completely played the role of a mediator between job crafting and work engagement.

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